

**IMPACT OF COVID-19 LOCKDOWN ON UNWANTED PREGNANCIES AMONG
WOMEN OF CHILDBEARING AGE (15-49 YEARS) IN RIVERS STATE**

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Abstract

This study examined the impact of COVID-19 lockdown on unwanted pregnancies among women of childbearing age (15 - 49 years) in Rivers State. Descriptive survey design was employed for the study. The population consisted of 1000 women of child bearing age (unmarried and married) in Kula kingdom. Purposive sampling technique was employed to obtain the sample. The sample size was 286 respondents (unmarried 150 and married 136) which were obtained through the Taro Yamane formula and a structured questionnaire was used to collect data. A reliability coefficient of 0.77 was obtained to show that the instrument was reliable using Pearson Product Moment Correlation Statistic. Data collected were analysed using mean, standard deviation, z-test to test the hypothesis. Findings indicated that causes of unwanted pregnancy were eagerness of adolescent female, peer group influence, poverty, lack of sexuality education and lack of parental supervision. It was recommended that sexuality education be taught in junior and senior secondary schools, age group meetings, churches, mosques, women gatherings.